

Design and Analysis of Steel Bridge Over Gurupura River

Karthik Acharya, Abhijith J Ullal, Lakshmi Baliga, Shravan S, Karthik Shetty, Inchargeland K

Department of Civil Engineering, SDIT, Kenjar, Mangalore

Abstract: A bridge must be designed to safely resist all loads and forces that may reasonably occur during its life. These loads include not only the weight of the structure and passing vehicles, but also load from natural causes, such as wind and snow. The loads may act individually but more commonly occur as a combination of two or more loads applied simultaneously. The project discussed analysis and design of steel truss bridge, the bridge is to designed over the GURUPURA river. The length of the bridge to be designed for about 190m. The analysis was done by STAAD Pro program. The project studies maximum axial forces, shear forces, torsional values & moment.

Keywords: Steel Bridge, Staad Pro,

1.Introduction

Steel bridges are widely used around the world in different structural forms with different span length, such as highway bridges, railway bridges, and footbridges. The main advantages of structural steel over other construction materials are its strength, ductility, easy fabrication, and rapid construction. It has a much higher strength in both tension and compression than concrete, and relatively good strength to cost ratio and stiffness to weight ratio. Steel is a versatile and effective material that provides efficient and sustainable solutions for bridge construction, particularly for long span bridges or bridges requiring enhanced seismic performance. The structural steel for steel bridges should be selected according to the required material properties or the stress state where used, environmental conditions at the construction site, corrosion protection method, construction method, etc. The physical properties of structural steel such as strength, ductility, toughness, weldability, weather resistance, chemical composition, shape, size, and surface characteristics are important factors for designing and construction of steel bridges. Three categories of structural steel are often used for steel bridge construction including carbon steel, high-strength steels, and heat-treated carbon steels.

2. Methodology

Design Data: The structural analysis and design of steel bridge has been done with the help of STAAD Pro software. The structure is located in seismic zone III on a site with medium soil. Structural plan is shown in figure 1.

Figure.1 a.Structural Plan and b.Site Location

Structure Details Length = 189.00m Width = 9.00m Height = 8.00m No. of lane = 2 nos. Width of lane = 3.5.00m Width of footpath = 1.5.00m Density of concrete = 25.00 kN/m³ Grade of steel = Fe500.

Earthquake Data Zone = III Importance Factor = 1.00 Response Reduction Factor = 5.00 Type of soil = Type II (medium). The proposed site is located in Kenjar, Mangalore. Soil Condition Since river soil is soft soil. Anchorage blocks will be placed in the soil. Since it is arch bridge it will only have contact with anchorage.

Loads taken for the design: Dead load, live load, imposed load, earthquake load, wind load.

3.1. Thumb Rules and Preferred Dimensioning for Steel Structure

- **Span-to-Depth Ratio:** It typically ranges from 15:1 to 20:1 for simple beam or girder bridges. For longer spans or more complex bridge types, such as trusses or arches, the ratio may vary.
- **Girder Depth:** The depth of steel girders should be optimized to achieve structural efficiency. The depth of the girder can be approximately 1/15 to 1/20 of the span length. However, this can vary depending on the bridge type, loading conditions, and other design considerations.
- **Clear Roadway Width:** The clear roadway width of the bridge should accommodate the anticipated traffic volume and lane requirements. A minimum of 3.6 meters (12 feet) per lane is often preferred for highways and major roads.
- **Live Load Distribution:** The distribution of live loads on the bridge should be considered. For simply supported steel bridges, a distribution factor of 0.7 is often used to determine the maximum moments and shears in the girders.
- **Deck Thickness:** The thickness of the steel bridge deck is typically determined based on the desired durability, aesthetics, and maintenance requirements. The deck thickness can range from 75mm to 150mm (3 to 6 inches) for typical highway bridges.
- **Vertical Clearance:** The vertical clearance of the bridge should provide sufficient space for the passage of vehicles or other structures beneath the bridge. A minimum vertical clearance of 5.2 meters (17 feet) is often recommended for highway bridges.

3.2. Modelling Of Structure Using Staad Pro

Line diagram was formed in Auto CAAD. Then it is imported to Staad in DXF format.

Then property was given arch was formed and replicated and model was formed.

Figure.3 -3D model – of steel bridge using STAAD

3.3 Support Specification: In present work fixed supports is provided. The support reactions are taken from the analysis and anchorage designed.

Figure 4a Top view of supports provided

Figure 4b Load application

Calculation of Wind Load As per IS 875 (part III):1987, appendix A

Figure 5a.&b a) Wind load application

b) Earthquake load application

Analysis STAAD Pro after analyzing the structure the results will be stored in post processing command. The structure is subjected to a static load case. The transfer of load follows a conventional path in order to reach support and ultimately ground. While transferring the load acting on the structure, the structure is subjected to internal forces like Axial forces, Shear forces, Bending and torsional moments. Structural analysis deals with analyzing these internal forces in the members of the structure.

Figure 6a&b a) Deflection diagram

b) Bending Moment Diagram

6c) Shear Force Diagram

3. Results and Discussion

Section Design Member 209 (Compression Member)

<p>Member 209 (Compression Member)</p> <p>Effective length $l = 3.15104\text{m}$</p> <p>Axial load $P = 1663.245\text{KN}$</p> <p>Grade of Steel Fe 500, $f_y = 250\text{N/mm}^2$</p> <p>$f_{cd} = 150\text{N/mm}^2$</p> <p>(1) Design of column</p> <p>Area of column required $\frac{1663.24 \times 10^3}{150}$</p> <p>$= 11088.3\text{mm}^2$</p> <p>$\therefore$ Area of one section $= 5544.15\text{mm}^2$</p> <p>Select ISMC400@483.6N/m</p>	<p>Properties :-</p> <p>Area of the section, $A = 6293\text{mm}^2 > 5544.15\text{mm}^2$,</p> <p>Height of the section, $h = 400\text{mm}$,</p> <p>Width of web, $b_w = 100\text{mm}$,</p> <p>Thickness of the flang, $t_f = 15.3\text{mm}$,</p> <p>Thickness of the web, $t_w = 8.6\text{mm}$</p> <p>$I_{zz} = 150.828 \times 10^6\text{mm}^4$,</p> <p>$I_{yy} = 5.048 \times 10^8$,</p> <p>$r_{zz} = 154.8\text{mm}$,</p> <p>$r_{yy} = 28.3\text{mm}$,</p> <p>$C_{yy} = 24.2\text{mm}$</p> <p>Let S be distance b/w channel</p> <p>$r_{yy} = r_{zz} + l_{zz} = I_{yy}$</p> <p>$2I_{zz} = 2 \left[I_{yy} + A \left(\frac{S}{2} - C_{yy} \right)^2 \right]$</p> <p>$150.828 \times 10^6 = \left[(5.048 \times 10^8) + (6293 \left(\frac{S}{2} - 24.2 \right)^2) \right]$</p> <p>$S = 353\text{mm}$</p>
<p>(2) Safety of section:</p> <p>$\Lambda = \frac{kl}{r_{zz}} = \frac{1.05 \times 3151.04}{154.8} = 21.37$</p> <p>Design compressive stress, $f_{cd} = 222.219\text{N/mm}^2$</p> <p>Design compressive load, $P_d = A_e \times f_{cd}$</p> <p>$= 2 \times 6293 \times 222.219$</p> <p>$= 2796.85 \times 10^3\text{N} > 1663.245\text{KN}$</p> <p>$\therefore$ Safe</p>	

(3) Lacing Design

Assuming 20mm dia bolts

△ Gauge length = 50mm

△ Horizontal distance b/w bolt line = 353 - 50 - 50 = 253mm

Spacing b/w lacing bars = 253tan45° = 253

$L_{eq} = 506\text{mm}$

$$\frac{I_{yy}}{I_{xx}} = 0.7 \times \frac{I_{yy}}{I_{xx}}$$

$$\frac{506}{253} = 17.88 > 0.7 < 20.35 = 14.245$$

△ Safe

Transverse shear to be resisted by lacing

$$V_t = 2.5\% \text{ of axial load}$$

$$\frac{2.5}{100} \times 1663.245 = 41.58\text{KN}$$

Transverse shear in each panel = $\frac{41.58 \times 10^3}{2} = 20.79 \times 10^3\text{N}$

Compressive force in the lacing bar = $20.79 \times 10^3 \times \frac{1}{\cos 45^\circ} = 29.401 \times 10^3\text{N}$

For 20mm dia bolts

Min width of lacing = 3 × 20 = 60mm

Min thickness = $\frac{1}{40} \times (253 \times \csc 45^\circ) = 8.9 \sim 9\text{mm}$

△ Provide lacing bars of 60 × 9mm plate

Min radius of gyration

$$R = \frac{I_{yy}}{\sqrt{I_{yy}}} = \frac{9}{\sqrt{12}} = 2.6\text{mm}$$

△ Slenderness ratio of lacing bar

$$\Lambda = \frac{L_{eq}}{R} = \frac{253 \csc 45^\circ}{2.6} = 137.61 < 145$$

△ Safe

(5) Tie plate

$$= S - 2(C_{yy}) = 353 - 2(24.02)$$

$$= 304.6\text{mm}$$

Assuming 30mm edge distance at each end

Depth of tie plate = 304.6 + 2(30) = 364.6mm

Total width of tie plate, S = 353mm

Thickness of tie plate = $\frac{1}{50} \times 353 = 7.06 \sim 8\text{mm}$

△ Provide tie plate 370 × 353 × 8mm at both end with #6-16mm dia

MEMBER 209

UNITS - in mm

Fig no.4.2: Detailing of section 209

Member 210 (Compression Member)

Effective length $l = 3.15104\text{m}$

Axial load $P = 889.874\text{KN}$

Design compressive strength

$$= A \cdot f_{cd} = 60 \times 9 \times 68.136 = 36.70 \times 10^3 > 29.401 \times 10^3\text{N}$$

△ Safe

(4) Check for tension in lacing bars

Design of strength of plate against rupture

$$T_{br} = \frac{0.6 f_u b n t_p}{\gamma_{M2}} = \frac{0.6 \times 410 \times 25 \times 9}{1.25}$$

$$= 100.56 \times 10^3\text{N}$$

Design strength of plate against yielding

$$T_{br} = \frac{0.6 f_y b n t_p}{\gamma_{M1}} = \frac{0.6 \times 250 \times 25 \times 9}{1.1}$$

$$= 29.40 \times 100.56\text{KN}$$

△ Hence OK

Design strength of 20mm dia bolt

(1) In double shear = $2 \left[\frac{f_u A_{nt}}{1.75} \right]$

$$= 2 \left[\frac{410 \times 300}{1.75 \times 1.25} \times 0.707 \times 20^2 \right]$$

$$= 90.54 \times 10^3\text{N}$$

(2) In bearing = $2.5 k_b \times d \times t \times f_u \leq \frac{f_u A_{nt}}{1.25}$

$$= \frac{2.5 \times 410 \times 300 \times 9}{1.25}$$

$$= 73.8 \times 10^3\text{N}$$

△ Design strength of bolt = 73.8 × 10³N

△ No of bolt = $\frac{29.401 \times 10^3}{73.8 \times 10^3} = 0.4 \sim 1\text{No}$

(1) Design of column

Area of column required = $\frac{889.87 \times 10^3}{1.50}$

$$= 5932.49\text{mm}^2$$

△ Area of one section = 2966.49 mm²

Select ISMC-400@483.6N/m

Properties :-

Area of the section, $A = 33.01\text{mm}^2 > 2966.24\text{mm}^2$,

Height of the section, $h = 225\text{mm}$,

Width of web, $b_w = 80\text{mm}$,

Thickness of the flang, $t_f = 12.4\text{mm}$,

Thickness of the web, $t_w = 6.4\text{mm}$

$$I_{zz} = 26.946 \times 10^6\text{mm}^4,$$

$$I_{yy} = 1.872 \times 10^6,$$

$$r_{zz} = 90.3\text{mm},$$

$$r_{yy} = 28.3\text{mm},$$

$$C_{yy} = 23\text{mm}$$

Let S be distance b/w channel

$$r_{yy} = r_{zz} \cdot I_{zz} = I_{yy}$$

$$2I_{zz} = 2 \left[I_{yy} + A \left(\frac{S}{2} - C_{yy} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$26.946 \times 10^6 = \left[(1.872 \times 10^6) + \left(3301 \left(\frac{S}{2} - 23 \right)^2 \right) \right]$$

$$S = 220\text{mm}$$

(2) Safety of section:

$$\Lambda = \frac{hl}{r_{zz}} = \frac{3.15061 \times 10^3}{90.3} = 34.89$$

Design compressive stress, $f_{cd} = 202.3745/\text{mm}^2$

Design compressive load, $P_d = A_e \times f_{cd}$
 $= 2 \times 33.01 \times 202.3745$
 $= 1336.07 \times 10^3 \text{ N} = 889.874 \text{ KN}$

∴ Safe

(3) Lacing Design

Assuming 20mm dia bolts

∴ Gauge length = 40mm

∴ Horizontal distance b/w bolt line

$= 220 - 40 - 40 = 140\text{mm}$

Spacing b/w lacing bars = $140 \tan 45^\circ \times 2$

$L_c = 280\text{mm}$

$\frac{L_c}{r_{yy}} = 0.7 \times \frac{L_c}{r_{yy}}$

$\frac{280}{22.8} = 11.76 < 0.7 \times 14.89 = 10.423$

∴ Safe

Transverse shear to be resisted by lacing

$V_t = 2.5\%$ of axial load

$= \frac{2.5}{100} \times 889.874 = 22.26 \text{ KN}$

Transverse shear in each panel = $\frac{22.26 \times 10^3}{2} = 11.13 \times 10^3 \text{ N}$

Compressive force in the lacing bar = $11.13 \times 10^3 \times \frac{1}{\sin 45^\circ} = 15.73 \times 10^3 \text{ N}$

For 20mm dia bolts

Min width of lacing = $3 \times 20 = 60\text{mm}$

Min thickness = $\frac{1}{40} \times (140 \times \cos 45^\circ) = 4.9 \sim 5\text{mm}$

∴ Provide lacing bars of 60×5mm plate

Also see the following

From table 9(c) of IS 800

For $\frac{h}{r_{yy}} = \frac{420 \times 10^3}{24.8} = 17.28$

And $f_y = 250 \text{ N/mm}^2$

By interpolation

$f_{cd} = 201.536 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Load carrying capacity of I-section

$P_d = A_e \times f_{cd}$

$= 600 \times 201.536$

$= 120917.8 \text{ N} = 120.917 \sim 120.92 \text{ KN}$

Hence design is safe.

Section 522 (compression member)

Effective Length = 1.150m

Axial Load, P = 401.528KN

Assuming slenderness ratio = 70

The corresponding design compressive stress for bending about y-axis (with buckling curve-c) (C) OF IS 800

$f_{cd} = 152 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Required area = Factorial load $\times \frac{1}{f_{cd}}$

$= \frac{401.528 \times 10^3}{152} = 2641.63 \text{ mm}^2$

ISRC 250(500) 3N

$A = 6496 \text{ mm}^2, I_x = 250, I_y = 250, r_{xx} = 9.7 \text{ mm}, r_{yy} = 109.1 \text{ mm}, z_{xx} = 54.9 \text{ mm}$

Buckling design curve c is applicable

From table 9(c) of IS 800

For $\frac{h}{r_{yy}} = \frac{420 \times 10^3}{24.8} = 17.28$

$R = \frac{f_y}{\gamma_{m1}} = \frac{250}{1.1} = 227.27 \text{ N/mm}^2$

∴ Slenderness ratio of lacing bar

$\lambda = \frac{L_c}{r} = \frac{280 \times 10^3}{2.88} = 97222.22$

∴ Safe

$f_{cd} = 68.225 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Design compressive strength

$= A_e \times f_{cd} = 60 \times 68.225 = 4093.5 \times 10^3 \text{ N}$

∴ Safe

(4) Check for tension in lacing bars

Design of strength of plate against rupture

$T_n = \frac{0.6 f_u b t_n}{\gamma_{m2}} = \frac{0.6 \times 410 \times 20 \times 2}{1.25}$

$= 6336 \times 10^3 \text{ N}$

Design strength of plate against yielding

$T_{d1} = \frac{A_g f_y}{\gamma_{m1}} = \frac{400 \times 250}{1.1} = 90909.09 \times 10^3 \text{ N}$

$56.088 \times 100.5 \text{ KN}$

∴ Hence OK

Design strength of 20mm dia bolt

(1) In double shear = $2 \left[\frac{f_u}{\sqrt{3}} \times A_{nb} \right]$

$= 2 \left[\frac{410}{\sqrt{3} \times 1.25} \times 0.78 \frac{\pi}{4} \times 20^2 \right]$

$= 90.54 \times 10^3 \text{ N}$

(2) In bearing = $2.5 k_b \times d \times t \times f_u \times \frac{1}{\gamma_{m2}}$

$= \frac{2.5 \times 0.5 \times 20 \times 2 \times 410}{1.25}$

And $f_y = 250 \text{ N/mm}^2$

By interpolation

$f_{cd} = 201.5 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Load carrying capacity of I-section

$P_d = A_e \times f_{cd}$

$= 6496 \times 201.5$

$= 1308.9 \text{ KN} = 1309.17 \sim 1309.17 \text{ KN}$

Hence design is safe.

Design strength of 20mm dia bolt

(1) In double shear = $2 \left[\frac{f_u}{\sqrt{3}} \times A_{nb} \right]$

$= 2 \left[\frac{410}{\sqrt{3} \times 1.25} \times 0.78 \frac{\pi}{4} \times 20^2 \right]$

$= 90.54 \text{ KN}$

(2) In bearing

$= \frac{2.5 \times k_b \times d \times t \times f_u}{\gamma_{m2}}$

$= \frac{2.5 \times 0.5 \times 20 \times 2 \times 410}{1.25} = 73.8 \text{ KN}$

Design strength of bolt = 73.8KN

No. of bolts = $\frac{1.04 \times 10^7}{73.8 \times 10^3} = 0.01 \sim 1 \text{ bolt}$

(3) Tie plate

$= S - 2(C_{yy}) = 105 - 2(14) = 77 \text{ mm}$

Assuming 30mm edge distance at each end and depth of tie plate

$= 77 + 2(30) = 137 \sim 140 \text{ mm}$

Total width of plate $140 \times 105 \times 2 \text{ mm}$

Provide tie plate $140 \times 105 \times 2 \text{ mm}$

At both ends with no. of bolt of 16mm dia.

4.2.2 Design of bolted connections

For section 209

Using M_{20} bolts, $d = 20\text{mm}$, $d_0 = 22\text{mm}$

For Fe410 grade steel, $f_u = 410\text{Nmm}^2$

$$\text{Design strength of bolt in double shear } V_{dsb} = \frac{V_{nsb}}{\gamma_{mb}} = \frac{f_{ub}(n_s \times A_{nb})}{\sqrt{3}\gamma_{mb}}$$

$$= \frac{400 \times 2 \times 245}{\sqrt{3} \times 1.25} = 90.52\text{KN}$$

(2) Design bearing strength of bolt

$$V_{dpb} = \frac{2.5k_b d t f_u}{\gamma_{mb}} = \frac{2.5 \times 0.507 \times 20 \times 8.6 \times 410}{1.25} = 71.507\text{KN}$$

Hence strength of bolt = 71.507KN

$$\text{No. of bolt} = \frac{1663.245}{71.507}$$

$$= 23.25 \sim 24\text{no}$$

For Section 29

Design of bolted connections

Using M_{20} bolts, $d = 20\text{mm}$, $d_0 = 22\text{mm}$

For Fe410 grade steel, $f_u = 410\text{Nmm}^2$

$$\text{Design strength of bolt in double shear } V_{dsb} = \frac{V_{nsb}}{\gamma_{mb}} = \frac{f_{ub}(n_s \times A_{nb})}{\sqrt{3}\gamma_{mb}}$$

$$= \frac{400 \times 2 \times 245}{\sqrt{3} \times 1.25} = 90.52\text{KN}$$

(2) Design bearing strength of bolt

$$V_{dpb} = \frac{2.5k_b d t f_u}{\gamma_{mb}} = \frac{2.5 \times 0.507 \times 20 \times 3 \times 410}{1.25} = 24.944\text{KN}$$

Hence strength of bolt = 24.944KN

$$\text{No. of bolt} = \frac{59.362}{24.944} = 2.3 \sim 3\text{no.}$$

Section 623

Load = 597.175KN, $t_f = 9.7\text{mm}$

Design strength of bolt in double shear

$$V_{dps} = \frac{2.5k_b d t f_u}{\gamma_{mb}} = \frac{2.5 \times 0.507 \times 20 \times 9.7 \times 410}{1.25} = 80.65\text{KN}$$

$$\text{No. of bolt} = \frac{597.175}{80.65} = 7.40 \sim 8\text{no}$$

FRONT VIEW

UNITS - in mm

Fig no.4.3: Front view of connection

Figure.7 Axial load on member 201

4. CONCLUSION

- Structure was analysed using STAAD Pro.
- Design and calculation of section is done manually.
- Design of pavement is done using SCADDS 2.0 software. • Anchorage is designed using STAAD Pro.
- Detailing is done in AutoCAD.

References

- [1] N. Subramanian “Steel Structures Design and Practice”.
- [2] IS 800 (2007): General Construction of Steel.
- [3] R. Agor “Steel Table”.
- [4] IS 1893-1 (2002): Criteria for Earthquake Resistant Design of Structures.
- [5] IS 875(part 1): 1987, “Code practice for Design loads for buildings and structures”(Dead loads).
- [6] IS 875(part 2): 1987, “Code practice for Design loads for buildings and structures”(Imposed loads).
- [7] IS 875(part 3): 1987, “Code practice for Design loads for buildings and structures” (wind loads).
- [8] IS 875(part 4): 1987, “Code practice for Design loads for buildings and structures”(Snow load).
- [9] IRC:6-2017: LOADS AND LOAD COMBINATIONS.
- [10] Mirela D. Thumbeva, Ashley P. Thrall, Theodore P. Zoli, Investigating the redundancy of steel truss bridges composed of modular joints, Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering and Earth Sciences, University of Notre Dame,Notre Dame IN 46556, USA (2021).
- [11] Oskar Skoglund, John Leander, Raid Karoumi, Optimizing the steel girders in a high strength steel composite bridge, Division of Structural Engineering and Bridges,KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm 100 44, Sweden (2020).
- [12] Michelle Y. X. Chien, Scott Walbridge, Bertram Kuhn, Comparison of International Brittle Fracture Design Code Provisions for Steel Bridges, Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Canada (2022),
- [13] Xu S, Yang Y, Lu Deng, Liu B, Experimental Study on the Steel-Concrete Composite Girder Joint of a Single Pylon Cable-Stayed Bridge, College of Civil Engineering, Hunan University, Hunan, China (2017).
- [14] Naveen Kumar. S, Naveenkumar M, Puviarasan D, Rajamithraa M. S, Mrs. S.Devi, Analysis and Design of Skew Steel Bridge, Department of civil Engineering, Adiyamaan college of Engineering, Hosur (2014).
- [15] Sonia S, S Devi, S Suresh Babu, ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF STEEL BOX GIRDER BRIDGE USING TEKLA STRUCTURES, Dept. of Civil Engineering, Adhiyamaan College of Engineering, Hosur, Tamilnadu (2020).